

Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions (*in English*)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Christian Oltra

CISOT - Socio-Technical Research Centre / CIEMAT

Moderator: Arsev U. Ayginoglu

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, June 10, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/g6QRkcovRBu7JbBTA>

Moderation: Asst. Prof Dr. Arsev Umur Aydinoglu

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 09 June 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 09 June 2022.

Abstract: The European Commission has supported a better integration of non-economic energy-Social Sciences and Humanities into the energy research and policy process in the last years. It is considered crucial that SSH topics and approaches are included in European funding strategies, and that the SSH community is included in selection processes. Energy transitions are not only technological and ecological challenges but also political and social ones. We need to draw on many kinds of knowledge – including evidence from the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). In this presentation, we explore the challenges in the integration of SSH approaches and methods in the energy domain and discuss several topics where energy SSH have produced more valuable results.

Speaker:

Christian Oltra is PhD in Sociology. He works as a social researcher at the Socio-technical Research Centre at CIEMAT. His main research areas are the social reactions to technological and environmental issues, environmental risk perception, the social acceptance of new energy technologies, and energy behavior. He is currently participating in various research projects dealing with the social acceptance of energy technologies and environmental risk. He has been involved in the EU Projects “New participation and communication strategies for neighbors of CO2 capture and storage operations- NEAR CO2”, “Pachelbel-Policy Addressing Climate Change and Learning about Human Behaviour and Everyday Life, and “Hydrogen acceptance in the transition phase - HYACINTH Project”. He has published research articles in journals such as Energy Policy, Energy Research and the Social Sciences, Environmental Monitoring and Assessment and the Journal of Risk Research.

About SolarTwins- TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhsnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Sustainable Energy and Climate Policies in the Light of Changing Global and Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAK _{TR} : Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	S. Banu AKKAŞ, Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Sustainability and AgroPV Potential in Turkish Agriculture From Social Sciences Perspective Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective

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